

Segmentation and characteristic extraction for Schumann Resonance transient events[★]

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ABSTRACT

In this article we propose a novel methodology for obtaining Schumann Resonances' relevant parameters from ELF transient register. Using this methodology, it is possible to extract a large amount of data and characterize individual transient events and their more relevant features. To use this methodology a new narrow band sensor is presented, centered in the 1st Schumann Resonance mode and specialized in capturing with high precision the associated transient events. The new methodology based on Hilbert transform and Heidler function is presented and used to segment and characterize each transient event. This method is validated first with an automatic classifier algorithm and then an extensive statistical analysis is performed. The validation process is shown as one of the possible applications of the methodology. The introduced set of narrow band hardware and software tools represents an important milestone for the study of transient events focused on a high amount of data.

1. Introduction

Schumann Resonances (SRs) are electromagnetic waves formed in the natural Earth-ionosphere cavity located in the *Extremely Low Frequency* (ELF) band, from 1 Hz to 100 Hz (Schumann [1952]). Global lightning activity has been established as the principal contributor to the resonances' electromagnetic energy (Ogawa et al. [1969]), whose strokes induce a strong electromagnetic disturbance that propagates along the atmosphere (Nickolaenko [2014]). The geometry and electromagnetic composition of the cavity determine its resonant frequencies (Tran and Polk [1979]). Many studies have been proposed to study the conductivity profile of the upper boundary of the cavity, both from a theoretical point of view (Kudintseva et al. [2018], Perotoni [2018]) and with a simulation approach (Goncharov et al. [2019], Kwisanga and Fourie [2017]).

Obtaining spectral information about SR and their associated natural phenomena is the typical methodology to study them, the reason why it has been widely addressed and is still the mainstream method of analysis. In Galuk et al. [2020], the authors proposed a model treatment for exploring the relationship between earthquakes and the modification of the SR's spectra, using a theoretical approach. The long-term variations are a popular subject of study (Koloskov et al. [2020], Bozóki et al. [2021]), where the goal is usually to experimentally prove the relationship between SRs and some natural phenomenon, relying on monitoring by two or more stations in different parts of the globe. Other authors are also interested in the frequency of regular variations either using one station (Anonymous et al. [2021]) or many (Tatsis et al. [2020]), without any particular focus on finding a connection with a specific event. Although spectral analysis is the most common approach for studying SR, a few studies rely on temporal registers to analyze the Earth-ionosphere signals (Anonymous et al. [2021]). Nonetheless, time-based methods are still in the minority.

The footprint of the global lightning activity on the spectrum is considered as the most critical phenomenon among

ELF transient activity (Price [2016], Greenberg and Price [2007], Hobara et al. [2001]). For the most relevant events in ELF, a classification was proposed by Ogawa in 1966 (Ogawa et al. [1966]).

- ELF-Flashes: High amplitude transients caused by the strong interaction with a close lightning discharge, recognized by the receiver saturated response.
- Q-bursts: Short transient events associated with a powerful lightning discharge that resonates several times around the globe (Nickolaenko [2014]), with an average rate of one per minute.
- ELF background noise: It is the ELF register's base signal due to the continuous discharges all over the Earth.

An example of a Q-burst and background noise can be seen in Fig. 1a. Q-bursts are identified based on the total contribution in *Power Spectral Density* (PSD); when the register is above an absolute value, it is classified as a Q-burst (Guha et al. [2017]). Guided by the value extracted from the previous reference, any event with a peak value higher than 2×10^6 pT could be identified as a Q-burst. 29 events identified as Q-burst were detected with the method developed by the previously mentioned research in the validation segment.

Among the phenomena listed on this classification, Q-bursts are the only ones that can be considered transient events and, at the same time, generate data to be researched. This reason is why most ELF transient event studies are focused on them. Boccippio et al. [1995] proposed a first step in the identification between Q-bursts and *Transient Luminous Events* (TLE). This first approach is based on a few observations and the individual analysis of each transient event. The next milestone on this topic was published in Guha et al. [2017]. The authors explore the relation between Q-bursts and the TLEs known as Sprites. They used two long-distant ELF and a TLE optical sensors. This approach also focused on studying high peaks in the ELF register individually. The relation between TLE, always associated with

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a *Positive cloud-to-ground* (CG+) discharge, and ELF events^{S133} has been established (Inan et al. [2010], Pasko et al. [2012],^{J34} Williams et al. [2007]). Specifically, There are three works^{S135} that have been carried out on the potential association be^{T36} tween Sprites and strong Q-bursts (Fukunishi et al. [1996],^{J37} Haldoupis et al. [2010], Surkov and Hayakawa [2020]). How^{T38} ever, some aspects of this relationship remain unexplained.^{S139}

On the other hand, little to no attention has been given^{S140} to the individual contribution of standard lightning events^{S141} to the ELF spectrum. It is a widely stated fact that SR radio^{S142} signal is the aggregated effect of many individual pulses^{S143} coming from global lightning activity (Nickolaenko [2014]),^{S144} It is also acknowledged that powerful lightning discharges^{S145} generate a specific pattern in the time domain; the previously^{S146} mentioned Q-bursts. When putting both facts together, it^{S147} seems logical being able to find a typical time domain pattern^{S148} in SR transient events that is directly related with lightning^{S149} events.^{S150}

Creating an automated methodology to identify and clas^{S151} sify the contribution of these individual pulses is the goal^{S152} of this paper. With that purpose in mind, a *Narrow-Band*^{S153} *Extremely Low Frequency* (NB-ELF) sensor has been devel^{S154} oped, featuring a band pass profile and centered in the first^{S155} SR mode (7.8 Hz), which contains the most spectral informa^{S156} tion of the phenomenon. The previously mentioned studies^{S157} about Q-bursts, performed using broadband sensors, show^{S158} how these transient events are most present in this frequency^{S159} band. This result leads to the assumption that by restricting^{S160} the sensor band to the first mode, transient events should^{S161} still be present and, since the rest of the frequencies are fil^{S162} tered, their presence should be more noticeable. A novel^{S163} methodology for the segmentation and feature extraction of^{S164} ELF transient register has been developed and presented here^{S165}. It has been developed having in mind the new technologies^{S166} for the treatment of a large amount of data, such as Deep^{S167} Learning or Big Data since these can be successfully ap^{S168} plied to a long time SR register and find day-to-day patterns,^{S169} seasonal differences or yearly changes. The automatization^{S170} purpose is another reason to restrict the sensor's frequency^{S171} band to the first mode. Knowing the average frequency of^{S172} the captured signal beforehand simplifies some steps of the^{S173} automatic classification, such as envelope extraction.^{S174}

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives a brief^{S175} overview of the studies published about lightning activity and^{S176} ELF transient events. The new narrowband ELF sensor and^{S177} the methodology developed are presented in section 3 with^{S178} the algorithm used to extract the ELF transient events. The^{S179} validation process is shown in the Results section 5 with par^{S180} ticular emphasis on the relation between groups of transient^{S181} events, followed by a discussion about the exposed result.^{S182} Finally, conclusions are drawn in the final section.^{S183}

2. Electromagnetic Interaction: Lightning, Ionosphere and ELF Band

The starting point for this methodology is the fact that^{S187} most ELF transient events are created by lightning discharge.^{S188}

Therefore, the recorded waveform in the ELF register is the lightning discharge signal convoluted with the impulse response of the Earth-ionosphere waveguide (propagation effect) and further convoluted with the impulse response of the sensor stage. This paper is based on the assumption that the Earth-ionosphere lightning response is proportional to the charge distribution of the lightning, albeit extended in time due to the propagation and absorption characteristics of the medium at its eigenfrequencies. This hypothesis is supported by the typical behavior of impulse-generated signals in any resonant system concerning fading times. Specifically, the transient events already analyzed in the literature. Powerful Q-bursts rise to their peak value almost instantly, and from there on, the signal amplitude decays exponentially, in the same fashion as lightning releases their charge.

Nonetheless, the discrepancies between lightning discharge and electromagnetic resonance must be acknowledged; the anisotropy and variability of the resonant cavity will modify the response accordingly. It has to be taken in consideration as well that the resonant waves travel over the poles and across the day-night termination. All these causes general effects that prevents the determination of a single frequency, like mode splitting Labendz [1998]. Regarding the capture of transient events specifically, it leads to a peak time depending on the distance to the lightning perturbation. However, assign the peak value to the lightning peak current or determine the distance to the source from the analysis' results is outside the scope of this research.

By following that train of thought, it can be stated that by understanding the characteristics of the natural source - lightning discharges - we can study its effects on the ELF register. The outlined relationship gives way to the hypothesis of every noticeable amplitude variation in the ELF signal being the consequence of a specific electromagnetic transient event which, as stated before, is the goal of this paper. This relationship is in line with the literature, where papers can be found proving the relationship between ELF events and lightning activity Ramarao and Chandrasekaran [2020], Bermudez et al. [2007].

Through the hypothesis exposed before, The relevant time parameters for ELF transients can be extracted from the behavior of individual lightning discharges. The most relevant parameters for lightning discharges are:

- **Rise time:** Rise time is calculated as the time difference between the moment current reaches ten % and 90 % of its maximum discharge value. Experimental data shows average values ranging from 2 μ s Wooi et al. [2019] to 5.6 μ s (Visacro et al. [2004]).
- **Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM):** The time measured between the points where the signal has a 50 % of its maximum value, which happens first in the rising part of the discharge the other in the falling part. Average values has been established experimentally from 23.8 μ s (Wooi et al. [2019]) to 53.5 μ s (Visacro et al. [2004]).
- **Peak Current:** There is considerable consensus about

Figure 1: Sensor Characterization: a: Transient register with NB Sensor ELF background noise (Green Line) and Q-burst (Red Line), b: Frequency Response of the Broad Band Sensor - gsen7NSEQR (Green Line) and NB-ELF Sensor - gsen8B0BGR2M (Blue Line) and c: Physical implementation of the NB-ELF sensor.

189 peak current being modeled by log-normal distribu-218
 190 tions, widely demonstrated in Slyunyaev et al. [2018]219
 191 This distribution has been also obtained experimentally220
 192 (Almeida et al. [2012]) with a 15 % peak probability221
 193 for 50 kA. High current discharges are usually mod-222
 194 eled by a separate log-normal distribution, with peak223
 195 values of 100 kA at 7 % probability (Chen et al. [2008]224
 196 Jerauld et al. [2005]). Among the different kinds of225
 197 electric discharges, CG+ are by far more powerful and226
 198 infrequent than *Negative cloud-to-ground* (CG-), with227
 199 peak current, discharges over 250 kA. 228

200 Another parameter that is relevant to define this relation229
 201 ship is the propagation effect of the Earth-ionosphere cavity.230
 202 It has been studied using Sprites as a reference. Sprites are231
 203 TLEs associated with strong discharges in the mesosphere.232
 204 The majority of Sprites last few μ s and the corresponding233
 205 ELF perturbation last around 1 s (Soula et al. [2015]). So the234
 206 propagation ELF event lasts 100000 times more than their235
 207 corresponded generated lightning discharge. 236

208 This behavior is directly inferred from the fact that sig-237
 209 nificant electromagnetic disturbances (Q-bursts) propagate238
 210 through the Earth-ionosphere cavity, which takes $1/7.8$ s239
 211 around eight times before it fades. This fading effect leads to240
 212 an average duration of 1 s. If this is considered the cavity's241
 213 impulse response, a similar response could be expected from242
 214 isolated, non-Q-burst lightning events. 243

215 3. Sensor Design 246

216 The ELF band has been one of the fields of study for247
 217 our research group in the last few years. Our group has248

done the design and implementation of a functional ELF
 observatory. This ELF observatory is able to record electro-
 magnetic signals from 1 Hz to 100 Hz for \mathcal{H}_{NS} and \mathcal{H}_{EW}
 orientations. A complete description of the functionality can
 be seen in [AnonymousRef]. This observatory was designed
 to obtain the maximum possible characteristics of the SRs up
 to the 6th mode, around 45 Hz. However, specific transient
 events are hardly distinguishable in the time domain due to
 the broadband sensor response, a limitation experienced by
 all broadband sensors.

Previous works were focused on obtaining the maximum
 spectral power information for the study of Schumann Reso-
 nances using a broadband sensor that can capture the maxi-
 mum number of SR modes. Due to its broadband characteris-
 tics, these sensors capture all modes of SR which is vital to
 study the signal as a whole. They also capture other signals
 in the same range such as power lines or trains interference
 (16.6 Hz and 50 Hz, respectively), usually filtered out by dig-
 ital means. That being said, to study SR transient events,
 this kind of strategy falls short. The interferences caused by
 other signals mask the effect transient events may have on the
 records, as well as the presence of the other modes. Digital
 filtering could be a solution, but it comes with a tradeoff in
 signal resolution, which is paramount for this study. We have
 studied and analyzed the data obtained by our broadband ELF
 observatory and reached the conclusion that the significant
 important part of the transient information is centered around
 the 1st SR mode. Following this line, we have developed a
 specific bandpass sensor with a narrow band profile and a
 central frequency of 7.8 Hz (NB-ELF). The sensing coil's
 features a Nylomag 77 core with a diameter of 45 mm and

249 longitude of 2 m. The coil's longitude is 0.7 m, with a total³⁰⁴
 250 diameter of 230 mm. A nylon bobbin supports the winding,³⁰⁵
 251 and it is done using copper wire of 0.92 mm including the³⁰⁶
 252 insulating layer, with a total of 57000 turns distributed in 75
 253 layers. This sensor's ELF records show amplitude variations³⁰⁷
 254 that don't feature in the ones produced by broad band sensors³⁰⁸
 255 These amplitude variations fit the expectations of finding³⁰⁹
 256 additional transient events, and they are measured with a tiny³¹⁰
 257 part of noise in comparison with the broadband sensor. Con-³¹¹
 258 cerning the band of interest for our purpose, around d7.8 Hz,³¹²
 259 the peak magnetic induction of the sensor as a function of³¹³
 260 frequency is $20 \mu\text{V pT}^{-1}$.³¹⁴

261 In other words, sensing the electromagnetic field with a³¹⁵
 262 sensor focused on the average central frequency of the first³¹⁶
 263 mode allows us to widen the system's response to extract³¹⁷
 264 the transient events with the highest possible resolution. The³¹⁸
 265 frequency comparison between the NB-ELF sensor and the³¹⁹
 266 one installed in the observatory mentioned above can be³²⁰
 267 observed in Fig. 1b.³²¹

268 The preliminary tests with the NB-ELF sensor showed³²²
 269 transient effects identifiable by a visual inspection. These³²³
 270 had enough amplitude variation over time to be differentiated³²⁴
 271 from ELF background noise but not enough to be considered³²⁵
 272 a Q-burst.³²⁶

273 For this study, different measurements were taken with the³²⁷
 274 described sensor and some portable acquisition equipment,³²⁸
 275 collecting data from the \mathcal{H}_{EW} axis of the magnetic field. The³²⁹
 276 sensor was deployed on the selected location and supported
 277 on two stands, specifically designed for this purpose. Data
 278 was stored locally on a computer in fifteen minutes' files. Due
 279 to wind presence affecting measurements, we have selected a
 280 register with the lowest disturbances. For this purpose, the
 281 measurement lengths 15 minutes and was performed in a
 282 completed isolated place without any possible human inter-³³¹
 283 ference in Location remove due to the anonymization process³³²
 284 An image of the physical implementation of the sensor can
 285 be seen in Fig. 1c.³³⁴

286 4. Methodology ³³⁷

287 The observations mentioned above contain some transient³³⁸
 288 signal events of Q-bursts and ELF background noise, mea-³³⁹
 289 surable in the frequency band of the first SR mode with our³⁴⁰
 290 sensor. This research aims to design a methodology for the³⁴¹
 291 segmentation and feature extraction of ELF transient events,³⁴²
 292 allowing us to study their most relevant features. As the³⁴³
 293 literature characterization of the ELF, transient events are³⁴⁴
 294 exclusive of the Q-bursts as the only type of ELF events, we³⁴⁵
 295 have studied this type of events in our registers to develop
 296 this tool. Then, the identification method will be applied to³⁴⁶
 297 the rest of identified transient events under the assumption³⁴⁷
 298 that they share lightning activity as their source. Lastly, the³⁴⁸
 299 extracted parameters for each transient event will allow the³⁴⁹
 300 validation through an automatic classification and a statistical³⁵⁰
 301 comparison.³⁵¹
 302 The complete methodology used through this research can³⁵²
 303 be seen in Fig. 2.³⁵³
 354

In order to show an application of the proposed method-
 ology, we have applied it on a NB-ELF register, with a time
 duration of fifteen minutes.

Stage 1: Hilbert Process

The first step to study transient events in the time domain
 through this research is extracting the envelope from the origi-
 nal register (Fig. 3). The need for envelope detection is based
 on the assumption that the central frequency is not constant,
 so an instantaneous frequency must be estimated for each
 identified event. The one that yielded the best results was the
 envelope detection process based on the Hilbert transform
 Brandwood [2013]. This method has been widely used in
 different fields, such as mechanical vibration and power grids.
 Briefly, the process consists on applying the Hilbert trans-
 form (Eq.1) to the original signal $x_s(t)$ to obtain the analytical
 signal $\hat{x}_s(t)$. Therefore, the amplitude is calculated using Eq.
 2, in which v_s is the envelope signal. Lastly, the register is
 downsampled with a factor of two, and an optimal low pass
 filter with a cutoff frequency of 3 Hz is applied. The process
 to extract the envelope can be seen in Fig. 3a. From the left
 column, it can be observed that all the information around
 7.8 Hz (at baseband) is preserved along with the Hilbert trans-
 form. The spectral information can be observed in the right
 column. It shows that the Hilbert algorithm is able to pre-
 serve the majority of the information in the first resonant,
 moved to 0 Hz due to the envelope detection process.

$$\hat{x}_s(t) = \frac{1}{\pi t} * x_s(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x_s(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

$$v(s) = \sqrt{|x_s^2| + |\hat{x}_s^2|} \quad (2)$$

Stage 2: Segmentation

At this stage, the process of identifying separate transient
 events is done by the fitting procedure. It focuses on finding
 signal peaks, considering it the most representative value of
 each ELF transient event. Obtaining the peak value is a pro-
 cessing algorithm that aggregates and weights the difference
 with previous and next peaks, peak prominence, the absolute
 value itself, and the separation between peaks. A transient
 event is narrowed down for each peak found by extracting its
 starting and ending points from local minima. Acquiring the
 boundary points of a transient event consists of evaluating
 all the relative minima within a specific range of the peak
 and choosing the most likely segmentation by using the dis-
 tance to the point and the prominence of the value itself. An
 example of this stage can be seen in Fig. 3b.

Stage 3: Heidler Fit

Up to this point, different segments are identified in the
 registers. Some of these segments can be classified as Q-
 bursts according to the definition in the literature Boccippio
 et al. [1995]. A process for modeling the envelope of the
 Q-burst ELF events has been applied, using fitting and cross-
 validation. In the last few years, the Heidler function has
 been used as an analytical interpretation of lightning dis-
 charges, being included in the IEC 62305 standard (Heidler

Figure 2: Methodology Flow diagram.

and Cvetić [2002]). Two parts compose the Heidler function, each corresponding to a separate phase of the natural discharge.

The Heidler function can be seen in Eq. 3, where $x(t)$ is the rise equation (Eq. 4) and $y(t)$ the fall equation (Eq. 5).

$$i(t) = \frac{I_o}{\eta} x(t)y(t) \quad (3)$$

$$x(t) = \frac{(t/\tau_1)^{nh}}{1 + (t/\tau_1)^{nh}} \quad (4)$$

$$y(t) = \exp(-\frac{t}{\tau_2}) \quad (5)$$

The variables take the following meaning:

- I_o : Current peak value.
- η : Correction factor for the peak current.
- τ_1 : Model fit rise time.
- τ_2 : Model fit fall time.
- nh : Current steepness factor.

The graphical representation and its most representative parameters can be seen in Heidler and Cvetić [2002].

Following the hypothesis at the start of the section, if Q-burst can be modeled as a Heidler function, it will acceptably fit the rest of the ELF transient events, assuming that both have the same origin. Then, it is possible to extract valuable parameters from the model of both types of events. An example of segment fit can be observed in Fig. 3c.

Stage 4: Select individual ELF Transient Events

ELF transient events are hard to identify in some cases due to the nature of the phenomena. There is not just one isolated phenomenon in multiple cases, and it is not possible to simultaneously identify a Heidler function with multiple transient

events. For this reason, the next layer of the algorithm is to classify and reject segments that do not meet the criteria of the response to an isolated natural phenomenon. As mentioned before, to choose the criteria, information about lightning discharges has been considered. The specific thresholds for these criteria are related to the natural phenomenon studied, and to fine tune them, we have relied on visual inspection of the results through several iterations. In the end, they were set up in a conservative way to prevent false positives, even if the number of transient events captured is not as high as it can be. For example, the ratio between fall time and rise time can not be greater than 20, and rise time cannot be shorter than one signal period, due to the sensor's sensitivity. The criteria used are based on the following aspects

- Fitting error.
- Ratio between FWHM and rise time.
- Ratio between fall time and rise time.
- Ratio between rise time and the period of the first resonance $\frac{1}{7.8 \text{ s}}$.
- Ratio between FWHM and the period of the first resonance $\frac{1}{7.8 \text{ s}}$.
- Envelope instant frequency value.
- Carrier instant frequency value.

Stage 5: Power Spectral Density (PSD)

Using the Heidler function fitting process, some characteristics of the transient events are extracted. Moreover, other interesting parameters can be obtained from the raw signal, so a signal analysis is performed directly to each ELF transient event's raw signal. The sum of the PSD of the 1st SR and the sum of the PSD in the rest of the spectrum are obtained using an averaging process of the spectral information in

Figure 3: Process for extracting ELF transient events a: Envelope detection algorithm in time domain (Left Column) and Frequency domain (Right Column), b: Segmentation of ELF transient events and c: Fit of ELF transient segment.

each segment. The parameters show the importance of the PSD around 7.8 Hz when a relevant ELF transient event is captured.

Stage 6: Hilbert - Huang transform

The premise of the signal under study having no constant frequency can be confirmed by inspecting the frequency spec-

trum of the signal (Fig. 4a), which is a broadband signal.

To analyze the changes of the broadband signal, the Hilbert-Huang transform (Bowman and Lees [2013]) has been used. It decomposes the signal in its intrinsic mode functions and compares the instantaneous frequency of each decomposition with the segment peak value. The Huang algorithm addition to the Hilbert base allows the system to decompose the signal in the sum of different relevant signals known as intrinsic functions. The Hilbert algorithm can extract the instantaneous frequency in each of these functions. The decomposition can be seen in Fig.4b and the instantaneous frequency of the first intrinsic mode function of the same register in Fig.4c.

Figure 4: Process for extracting and classifying ELF transient events, a: Frequency transform of an NB-ELF register, b: Intrinsic mode functions, c: Instantaneous frequency of the first intrinsic mode function.

Stage 7: ELF transient Parameters

From this point on, the study is based on analyzing the individual registers obtained in the previous stage. This stage is focused on identifying and extracting the most useful parameters. The utility of each parameter is based on the ability to characterize the ELF transient event, either about its power, duration, or frequency.

Stage 7.a: Hilbert - Huang Parameters

Two valuable parameters can be extracted based on the Hilbert - Huang transform mentioned in the previous stage. First, the instantaneous frequency, being the most relevant. It is typically around 7.8 Hz, although it commonly varies when a powerful ELF event starts. The second parameter is the envelope frequency. It refers to the period of variation in the amplitude of each ELF event. This frequency contains valuable information about the event's magnitude in the time domain.

Stage 7.b: Heidler Fit Parameters

As we can see in Eq. 3, Heidler function has 5 parameters. In order to characterize the ELF transient events, only two of these parameters are considered for this analysis: τ_1 and τ_2 . This reduction of variable size is important to diminish the complexity of the methodology and understand the relation between variables, although all possible variables could be taken into account. Using these two parameters as a baseline it is possible to calculate two more: FWHM and rise time. These two additional parameters provide a more practical description of the ELF transient event behavior. τ_1 , τ_2 , FWHM, and rise time parameters are included in the following stages. It is relevant to note that the rise time variable differs from the τ_1 due to the latter is directly from the model fit (hence, model fit rise time), whereas the rise time is calculated based on the time between the signal is between the 10% and the 90% during the rising part.

Stage 7.c: Raw signal parameters

Although an envelope detection process has been applied before the segmentation, some parameters provide more helpful information without the signal processing method. The unprocessed signal absolute peak value and the PSD values around 7.8 Hz and in the rest of the band have been selected.

5. Results and Discussion

We have applied the implemented methodology to a data register of the NB-ELF sensor with the aim of validating both the sensor and the methodology.

The result of the methodology will be presented, following by a brief discussion about the main milestones reached.

5.1. Results

The validation process is split into two parts, automatic classification, and statistical comparison. As it was mentioned before, the data is collected in segments of fifteen minutes, For this validation purpose, we have analyzed one segment in which we have isolated 553 Events.

5.1.1. Automatic Classification

The algorithm has extracted four parameters from the Heidler fit stage (two from the fit process and two calculated), three from the raw signal stage, and two related to the Hilbert-Huang transform stage. This process separates high-power ELF transients from the rest of ELF transients using the mentioned parameters.

First, dimensionality reduction is made using the PCA algorithm (Husson et al. [2010]). This method is an orthogonal linear transformation that transposes data into a new coordinate system that preserves the majority of the information. These new data dimensions are a linear combination of the original ones. In this methodology, dimensions are reduced from 9 (one for each parameter) to 2, thus finding the two-dimensional plane among the data space the data is most spread out.

The last step of this layer uses an automatic classification algorithm to find the two categories with their means as

close as possible (Lloyd [1982]). The technique employed is K-means, which is essentially a clustering approach related to unsupervised learning, but it can also be adapted to handle classification problems Kim and Gil [2019], Stoean et al. [2019]. The results can be seen in Fig. 5. The groups created by the classification algorithm are separable into the two most relevant reduced dimensions, as shown in Fig. 5a. Furthermore, when the two selected variables are peak value and band power, both groups are seemingly differentiated as well (Fig. 5b).

Figure 5: Automatic classification, a: Adimensional view classification and b: Peak value-band power dimensional view classification.

5.1.2. Statistical Comparison

Statistical analysis will be applied to the variables of the extracted segments.

Lightning Discharges Comparison

There are a few statistical classifications of lightning activity in the literature. To further test the assumption of lightning activity being the source of the analyzed transient events, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was used to choose the distribution that best describes the histogram representation of the parameters of each segment. This result is helpful in order to study natural excitation.

The most relevant parameters of a discharge are related to the current and the duration. In Fig. 6 one can see the distribution of related parameters in the ELF transient event.

Under this method, it can be determined that Fig. 6a finds its best fit in a log-normal distribution with a mean value of 0.6386 μT and a *Standard Deviation* (SD) of 0.34 μT .

Rise time histogram can be seen in Fig. 6b, which is also best fitted by the log-normal distribution, with the parameters of the distribution are a mean of 0.2435 s and a SD of 0.125 s.

The SR frequency spectrum is composed of the ELF transient event, which has more power in the band of the 1st SR (7.8 Hz). In Fig. 6c the distribution of the accumulated power in the band is presented. The most likely theoretical distribution using AIC is once again log-normal, and its resulting parameters are a mean of 2.23×10^9 pT and an SD of 0.3×10^9 pT.

Correlation Comparison

Fig. 7a shows the correlation between the peak value of the ELF transient event and their correspondent band power in the 1st SR band. The high correlation between the two can be observed with a strong dependency with $y \propto x^2$. Fitting with a quadratic function, the result shows a regression

Figure 6: Distribution of relevant parameters without high peak samples. a: Peak value, b: Rise time and c: Band power 1st SR.

Figure 7: Relation between peak value and band power: a: Band power in the band of the 1st SR resonance and b: Band power in the rest of the spectrum.

545 coefficient of $R^2 = 0.95$. On the other hand Fig. 7b correlates
 546 peak value with power over the rest of the band with an still
 547 high $R^2 = 0.88$. A high correlation was to be expected
 548 in both cases, since the peak value of a transient event is
 549 directly related with its power. The point of this correlation
 550 is to show how, by considering only the first mode of the
 551 SR, the correlation improves and dispersion is reduced. In
 552 other words, it serves as further validation of the approach
 553 of studying these transient events by means of the first SR
 554 mode.

555 It is noticeable that the difference in the lower values of
 556 the x-axis does not follow a clear tendency. In the same way
 557 high peak values are more dispersed than the band power in
 558 the 1st SR.

Distributions Comparison

559 The critical parameters of each ELF transient event are compared
 560 against the peak value in Fig. 8. The peak value of a
 561 selected segment represents the amplitude of the transient
 562 event with high precision. In each graph, the red dots represent
 563 ELF transient events classified as non Q-bursts, while blue dots
 564 are classified as Q-burst. In all figures, the x-axis is the peak value.
 565 In Fig. 8a it is selected the FWHM related to the duration of the
 566 whole event. It is possible to distinguish that Q-bursts and non
 567 Q-bursts events are distributed similarly without any clear tendency.
 568 Rise time is present in Fig. 8b. We can see that Q-bursts are more
 569 likely distributed with rapid values of rise time, although non Q-burst
 570 are also present in the lower values of the time.

571 The instantaneous frequency presented in section 4 is used to extract
 572 the period's average frequency under analysis. The supposition is
 573 that transient events are determined to construct the complete SR
 574 spectrum, and the instantaneous frequency could identify a change
 575 in the frequency in short times as the duration of the event. The
 576 distribution of these parameters concerning the peak value can be seen
 577 in Fig. 8c. It is clear that Q-burst events are less dispersed than
 578 non-Q-burst events. However, it is under the same range of values.

581 non-Q-burst events. However, it is under the same range of values.

582 Envelope frequency is a concept related to a broadband signal that
 583 is considered a frequency that determines the envelope shape. The
 584 envelope frequency is shown in Fig. 8d. There is a clear tendency
 585 for Q-burst events to be highly situated in the lowest part of the
 586 frequency, while the non-Q-burst events are widely spread but with
 587 a slight focus on the lower values.

Figure 8: Distribution of key parameters for non Q-burst (red dots) and Q-burst (blue dots). a: FWHM, b: Rise time, c: Instantaneous Frequency and d: Envelope Frequency.

Quantile Comparison

590 Through quantile comparison it is possible to observe if data
 591 density distribution is similar even when the scale is entirely
 592

different. If the points are close to the $y = x$ curve, the distribution density between both parameters is similar. The classification applied to the tested segment identifies 19 segments as Q-burst and 526 as non-Q-burst. Applying the techniques mentioned in the last part of the previous section the differences and similarities between these two segment groups will be presented.

In Fig. 9, a comparison between the percentile distribution of the most critical parameters from each group of ELF transient events are shown. Statistical differences between the Q-burst and rest of the transient events can be seen in the case of band power (Fig. 9a) and Peak value (Fig. 9b). On the other hand, Envelope Frequency (Fig. 9c) and rise time (Fig. 9d), are more concentrated in the case of Q-burst. However, it is considerably surprising that in the instantaneous frequency (Fig. 9e), and FWHMT (Fig. 9f), the distributions show a common behavior with values close to the $y = x$ line. This points out how low powered transient events have a behavior which is similar to Q-bursts, but smaller in amplitude. This gives evidence to the hypothesis of other lightning (not only high discharges) leaving traces in the ELF spectrum.

Figure 9: Comparison of the percentile distribution of the key parameters between Q-burst and Normal transient events through qq-plots. a: Band power in 1st SR, b: Peak value, c: Envelope frequency, d: Rise time, e: Instantaneous frequency and f: FWHM.

5.2. Discussion

The previous results are consistent with the known facts of the SRs, and also support the hypotheses explained in the first sections of the article. They are good evidence of the methodology performance, making the segmentation process and parameters extraction a promising feature to the study of ELF transient events. In the scope of this paper, it is directly related to the identified transient events, but also the amount of generated data by the methodology gives way to study them further by using deep learning methods.

The classification presents a substantial difference over the standard deviation method (Guha et al. [2017]) on analyzed data using NB-ELF. When using the automatic classification after applying the segmentation and feature extraction

methodology with the 15 min of the NB-ELF register, the method identifies 19 transient events as Q-burst. On the contrary, the SD method identifies 29 Q-burst.

The result using the technique proposed in this article $1.27 \frac{Q\text{-burst}}{\min}$ is more consistent with the accepted ratio of $1 \frac{Q\text{-burst}}{\min}$ than with the SD technique $1.93 \frac{Q\text{-burst}}{\min}$.

An important marked observation to emerge from the data comparison was that the distribution of peak value from the regular transient events follows a log-normal distribution, which models the lightning peak current as well (Herrera-Murcia et al. [2017]). This result offers evidence in favor of the close relationship between the lightning discharge peak current and transient event peak value (Salut et al. [2013], Arshad et al. [2020]).

Our experiments are in line with the previous findings in the literature about lightning discharges times (Wooi et al. [2019], Heidler and Paul [2020], Wu et al. [2020]). The lightning discharge distribution shows a similar signal waveform as shown in Fig. 6b. The Lightning discharge duration is around 10000 times larger than the ELF transient events. This difference is mainly due to the propagation characteristics of the ionosphere.

The high correlation between the peak value and band power in the 1st SR mode is noteworthy because it shows evidence that the most significant contribution of the transient event belongs to this band. This fact is more so since the correlation using the rest of the spectrum shows lower values. Interestingly, it is noticeable for Q-bursts and evident for the rest of transient events. This correlation endorses the hypothesis that every ELF transient event contributes to some extent to the complete SR spectrum, as is indicated in other research (Pizzuti et al. [2021]).

Considering the above, the distribution of the parameters shown in Fig. 8 is very similar between Q-burst and the rest of the transient events. The dispersion shown is wider in the rest of the ELF transient events than in the Q-burst. These differences can partly be explained by the aliasing caused by the overlap of various transient events of low peak value within the same register. Q-burst events are less susceptible to this phenomenon due to their high peak value, making it very difficult for overlapped transient events to be noticeable. This difference lends support to the hypothesis that Q-bursts and the rest of the ELF transient events proceed from the same natural phenomena, in line with the literature (Boldi et al. [2018], Prácsér et al. [2019], Pracser et al. [2020]).

In the direct comparison of the obtained parameters (Fig. 9) between Q-burst and non-Q-burst ELF transient events, the following could be observed: As expected, the values of band power in the 1st SR mode and peak value are significantly reduced in the case of non-Q-burst events. The explanation lies in the nature of the Q-burst, related to high power lightning discharge. On the other hand, Envelope Frequency and rise time show higher dispersion in non-Q-bursts than in Q-bursts. The nature of the register points to overlapping as the source of this dispersion, although it is hard to provide a conclusive explanation for these values given the limitations mentioned above. All the transient events contribute to form the 1st

SR as it can be extracted from Fig. 8c. However, Q-burst events are more concentrated to the theoretical value 7.8 Hz. It could be explained by the power of these ELF transient events, which can propagate entirely more times than other ELF transient events (Ogawa and Komatsu [2007]).

FWHM is the only measurement that considers both the peak value and the duration of the ELF transient event, making this parameter the most relevant one. To stress the relevance of this parameter, Fig. 9f shows a strong high tendency between Q-bursts and non-Q-bursts. This result offers compelling evidence for ensuring that all the analyzed ELF transient events contribute on their own to the SR signal. Hence Q-burst events are just the most potent evidence of lightning discharges on the ELF register. Despite that, other lightning transient events exposed in section 2 are also measurable with an appropriate sensor such as the NB-ELF.

All these results reinforce how this methodology, along with a narrow band sensor, can produce vast amounts of data which can apply deep learning methods. In turn, this may allow finding common patterns with other phenomena or evaluating ELF transient events' self-variability.

6. Conclusions

To sum up, this paper presents a novel methodology to identify transient events in the ELF time signals and to characterize each by extracting its most relevant features. Transient event identification is complemented with the design of a narrow band sensor centered in the 1st mode of the Schumann Resonances, which enhances the signal-to-noise ratio capture of these events.

Through these tools, medium-low amplitude transient events have been identified in the ELF records, which despite being theorized, to the best of our knowledge, were never analyzed in detail. These transient events have been compared with the most studied ELF transient events (Q-bursts). A few specifics must be highlighted.

- The methodology successfully differentiates between Q-bursts and the other, more common transient events employing an automatic classification method.
- Nonetheless, the existing resemblances between the low amplitude transient events and those identified as Q-bursts point out how lightning discharges also produce the former.
- Furthermore, the number of identified transient events is consistent with the average estimate for lightning discharges per minute.
- To characterize each transient event, several different parameters are extracted. A tentative analysis of the importance of each parameter has been performed, with full width at half maximum being the most representative for the classification purpose.

Using this methodology over an extensive period, it is possible to obtain a large amount of data that can be processed

using machine learning techniques or analysis. The segmentation and feature extraction methodology can be used for a variety of different applications, and mainly to understand the relation between ELF transient events and ionosphere parameters, such as solar flux or virtual height of the ionosphere.

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1 Graphical Abstract

2 Segmentation and characteristic extraction for Schumann Resonance transient events

